

**EXPLICIT EVALUATION OF A QUADRATIC SUM OVER
CONGRUENT PAIRS MODULO A PRIME**

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Abstract

Let p be an odd prime number and let l be a positive integer such that $\gcd(p, l) = 1$. The main purpose of this note is to prove an identity for the sum

$$\sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b \equiv al \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{b}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right).$$

1. Introduction and Main Result

Let p be an odd prime number and let l be a positive integer such that $\gcd(p, l) = 1$. Set

$$F(p, l) := \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b \equiv al \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{b}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right).$$

In particular, if $l = 1$, then we obtain the following simple closed-form expression:

$$F(p, 1) = \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{(p-1)(p-2)}{12p},$$

which naturally motivates the question of whether similar closed forms exist for general l coprime to p .

The aim of this short note is to establish such a closed formula for $F(p, l)$ in terms of p , l , and a trigonometric sum involving cotangent functions, through the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime and l be a positive integer such that $\gcd(p, l) = 1$. Then

$$F(p, l) = \frac{p^2 - 3lp + l^2 + 1}{12lp} - s(p, l), \tag{1}$$

where $s(p, l)$, which depends only on the value of $p \pmod l$, is the Dedekind sum

$$s(p, l) = \frac{1}{4l} \sum_{a=1}^{l-1} \cot\left(\frac{\pi a}{l}\right) \cot\left(\frac{\pi ap}{l}\right).$$

Example 2. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime. Then

$$F(p, p-1) = \frac{(p-1)(2-p)}{12p},$$

$$F(p, p+1) = \frac{(p-1)(p-2)}{12p}.$$

Example 3. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime. Then

$$F(p, 2) = \frac{(p-1)(p-5)}{24p};$$

in particular, $F(5, 2) = 0$.

Example 4. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime. Then

$$F(p, 3) = \frac{1}{36p} \times \begin{cases} (p-1)(p-10), & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{3} \\ (p-2)(p-5), & \text{if } p \equiv 2 \pmod{3} \end{cases};$$

in particular, $F(5, 3) = 0$.

Example 5. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime. Then

$$F(p, 4) = \frac{1}{48p} \times \begin{cases} (p-1)(p-17), & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{4} \\ p^2 - 6p + 17, & \text{if } p \equiv 3 \pmod{4} \end{cases};$$

in particular, $F(17, 4) = 0$.

Example 6. Let $p \geq 3$ be a prime. According to [3, Proposition 1] we have

$$F(p, 8) = \frac{1}{96p} \times \begin{cases} p^2 - 66p + 5, & \text{if } p \equiv 1 \pmod{8} \\ p^2 - 30p + 65, & \text{if } p \equiv 3 \pmod{8} \\ (p-5)(p-13), & \text{if } p \equiv 5 \pmod{8} \\ (p+5)(p+13), & \text{if } p \equiv 7 \pmod{8} \end{cases};$$

in particular, $F(5, 8) = F(13, 8) = 0$.

Moreover, one can use the results of Louboutin in [3] to derive closed-form expressions for $F(p, l)$ with $l \in \{5, 6, 10\}$.

2. Proof of Theorem 1.

We now present the proof of Theorem 1.

Proof of Theorem 1. Let l be a positive integer and let $p \geq 3$ be an odd prime that does not divide l . Set

$$M(p, l) := \frac{2}{p-1} \sum_{\chi \in G_p^-} \chi(l)L(1, \chi)L(1, \bar{\chi}),$$

where G_p^- denotes the set of cardinality $(p-1)/2$ of the odd Dirichlet characters modulo p . On the one hand, according to [2, Theorem 1] we have

$$M(p, l) = \frac{\pi^2(p^2 - 3(l + 4l s(p, l))p + l^2 + 1)}{6lp^2}. \tag{2}$$

On the other hand, for any odd primitive character χ , it is known (see, e.g., [4, Theorem 4.9]) that

$$L(1, \chi) = \frac{\pi i}{p} \tau(\chi) B_1(\bar{\chi}),$$

where $\tau(\chi)$ and $B_1(\chi)$ denote the Gaussian sum and the generalized Bernoulli number associated with χ , respectively. Substituting this into the definition of $M(p, l)$, we obtain

$$M(p, l) = \frac{-2\pi^2}{p^2(p-1)} \sum_{\chi \in G_p^-} \chi(l)\tau(\chi)\tau(\bar{\chi})B_1(\chi)B_1(\bar{\chi}). \tag{3}$$

Moreover, since

$$\tau(\chi)\tau(\bar{\chi}) = -p$$

(see, e.g., [4, Lemmas 4.7 and 4.8]), and since

$$B_1(\chi) = \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \chi(a) \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right)$$

(see, e.g., [4, Proposition 4.1]), Identity (3) becomes

$$M(p, l) = \frac{2\pi^2}{p(p-1)} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{b=1}^{p-1} \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{b}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \sum_{\chi \in G_p^-} \chi(al)\bar{\chi}(b). \tag{4}$$

Next, the orthogonality relations (see, e.g., [1, Theorem 6.16]) give us:

$$\sum_{\chi \in G_p^-} \chi(m)\bar{\chi}(n) = \begin{cases} (p-1)/2 & \text{if } n \equiv m \pmod{p} \text{ and } \gcd(m, p) = 1, \\ (1-p)/2 & \text{if } n \equiv -m \pmod{p} \text{ and } \gcd(m, p) = 1, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

This fact allows us to write (4) as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 M(p, l) &= \frac{\pi^2}{p} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b \equiv al \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \left(\left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) - \left(\frac{p-a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \right) \left(\frac{b}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \\
 &= \frac{2\pi^2}{p} \sum_{a=1}^{p-1} \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b \equiv al \pmod{p}}}^{p-1} \left(\frac{a}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right) \left(\frac{b}{p} - \frac{1}{2} \right). \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Identities (2) and (5) together yield the desired result. This completes the proof of the theorem. \square

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